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Effect of Social Media on Society

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In actuality, nobody can say for sure. These days, social media is so integral to our lives that it's difficult for us to imagine living without it. It has changed the way we obtain news about events happening in our communities, states, nations, and the world. It has also become our preferred method of communication with people we do not see every day. The impact of social media on society is multifaceted and far-reaching, influencing various aspects of individuals' lives, communities, and even entire nations. Social media platforms have indeed transformed the way people interact, communicate, and form relationships. Social media harms education, business, and the workplace due to the high number of crimes committed there and the amount of time spent on social networking activities. However, social media also has positive effects, which include facilitating open communication, expanding business contact opportunities, and making it simpler to stay in touch with friends and family.

Keywords: Social media, Phone, Computer, People, Society, Privacy and Security.

Introduction

Social media provides a global forum for people to voice their concerns and ideas. The word "social media" refers to the online and virtual community interactions between individuals or groups that involve the creation, sharing, and occasionally exchange of ideas, photographs, videos, and much more. Social media has become an essential part of people's lives surrounded by mobile devices and interactive social networking sites like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp. [W. Akram 2017].

Absolutely, social media has a significant influence on how we see the world, our culture, and our economy in the modern period. Social media is a new platform that

allows individuals to interact, relate to, and exchange ideas as well as organise for causes, ask for and provide guidance, and mobilise around issues. Social media has broken down barriers to communication, established decentralised channels of communication, and allowed everyone, even those living in oppressive nations, to engage democratically and have a voice.

Texting is preferred over phone calls, online chats are preferred over in-person meetings, and many people have replaced in-person interactions with easy platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Compared to traditional media, social networking sites like Facebook, Flickr, Twitter, and blogs have made it

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easier to create and share ideas quickly and widely [Shahjahan et. al., 2014].

Social media gives its users the ability to communicate with both known and unknown users. Here are some key points to consider regarding the impact of social media on society: Reduced Face-to-Face Interaction, Social Isolation, Impact on Mental Health, Superficial Relationships, Cyberbullying, Information Overload, and Opportunities for Positive Change. Social media has undoubtedly reshaped how we interact and communicate, both positively and negatively. Individuals must strike a balance between online and offline interactions and be mindful of the potential impact excessive social media use can have on their well-being and relationships.

The media serves as a tool for infotainment as much as entertainment. [Ugur 2017]. Social media has profoundly transformed society, shaping how people interact, learn, do business, and engage with social and political issues. While it offers numerous benefits, it also poses challenges that require careful consideration, regulation, and responsible use to mitigate potential negative impacts. Some of the Challenges and Concerns are,

- Privacy and Security: Social media raises concerns about data privacy, online security, and the misuse of personal information.
- Cyberbullying: The anonymity of the internet can lead to cyberbullying, which can have severe emotional and psychological consequences.
- Misinformation: Spread of false or misleading information, which can influence public opinion and decision-making processes.

Statement of the Problem

It has been noted that employees and students, respectively spend more time on social networking

sites than they do on their jobs and coursework. Thus, the goal of this study is to determine how social networks impact enterprises, other occupations and education.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the various social networking sites mostly used in our society.
- To understand the reasons for joining social networking.
- To find out whether social media has affected the people positively and negatively.

Research Methodology

India is home to a diversified population that includes both young and old, unemployed and employed, students, as well as workers in a variety of workplace environments. The researcher used a purposive sampling technique for the study. The sample size of the study is 90 respondents. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire.

Literature Review

[Amedie 2015] In this article the three primary categories are used by the author to illustrate the detrimental effects of social media. Initially, social media creates a fictitious sensation of virtual "connections" and flimsy friendships that cause emotional and psychological issues. Social media's second drawback is its tendency to become easily hooked, robbing users of their personal and family time and impairing their ability to interact with others, which can result in antisocial behaviour. Finally, social media has evolved into a tool that allows terrorists, pedophiles, and criminals to carry out illicit activities. The final study will focus on demonstrating the connection between criminal activity and the psychological issues brought on by social media.

[Anderson et. al., 2013] This study aims to investigate how polarisation of opinions about a topic may be caused by uncivil online interpersonal discussions and also explore these dynamics within the framework of nanotechnology, which makes for an intriguing case study as it's a relatively unknown subject that presents a unique opportunity to look at attitude formation and evolution. The majority of the public has a vague understanding of nanotechnology and frequently forms opinions about it using heuristics, or entertainment shortcuts, like valuing certain scientific concepts or predispositions.

[Hwang et al., 2015] This study confirmed that social media plays a significant role in encouraging people to join social movements. There was a higher intention to participate among social media users. The results demonstrated that social media enhanced social capital, which modifies the association between social media use and involvement in social movements. The hierarchical regression's outcome demonstrates that the intention to take part in social movements was significantly influenced by bridging social capital. Additionally, it was confirmed that bridging social capital had a moderating effect; those who intended to participate in social activities were more likely to.

[Siddiqui et al. 2016] In this paper the author discusses every facet of social networking, including both its advantages and disadvantages and also discusses the broad effects that various media will have on society. A particular field such as business, education, society, and youth is the focus of attention.

[Shahjahan et al., 2014] In this article the author illustrates how social media affects people's choices, communication, comfort level, and ability to save time. In recent years, social media, also known as "social networking," has almost entirely replaced traditional forms of communication in our daily lives. It functions similarly to other media, including

radio, television, and newspapers, but it goes far beyond simple idea and information sharing.

Results And Discussion

Table No. 1
Classification based on age

S.No	Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Age	Below 20 Years	5	6
2		20 – 30 Years	10	11
3		30 – 40 Years	25	28
4		Above 40 Years	50	56
Total			90	100

Source: Primary Data

From the analysis, it was found that 56% of the respondents come under the category of above 40 Years, 28% of the respondents come under the category of 30 to 40 Years, 11% of the respondents come under the category of 20 to 30 Years and 6% of the respondents come under the category below 20 years.

Table No. 2
Classification based on occupation

S.No	Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Occupation	Professionals	27	30
2		Teachers	40	44
3		Students	15	17
4		Unemployed	5	6
5		others	3	3
Total			90	100

Source: Primary Data

From the analysis, it was found that 44% of the respondents were teachers, 30% of the respondents were professionals, 17% of the respondents were students, 6% of the respondents were unemployed and 3% of the respondents were others.

Table No. 3
Most prefer Social Networking Sites

Social Networking Sites		
S.No	Networkin g Sites	Rank
1	Facebook	1
2	Friendster	6
3	Twitter	3
4	Youtube	4
5	Whatsapp	2
6	Linkendin	5

Source: Primary Data

“Facebook” is occupied top position followed by Whatsapp, Twitter, Youtube, Linkendin and Friendster respectively.

Table No. 4
Major advantages of using Social Networking Sites

S.No	Advantages	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Promotes open communication	43	48
2	Allow for the expansion of business contacts	27	30
3	It makes it easy to communicate with family and friends	20	22
Total		90	100

Source: Primary Data

Social networks enable open communication, allow for the expansion of professional contacts, and make it easier to stay in touch with family and friends. All of these benefits have a good impact on society since they stimulate the economy and foster love and connection among friends and family.

Table No. 5
Reasons for joining social networks

S.No	Reasons	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Locate old friends	41	46
2	Meet new people	25	28
3	Talk the day away	6	7
4	Make photo albums and share pictures	10	11
5	Seek advice	5	6
6	Assist others	3	3
Total		90	100

Source: Primary Data

From the analysis, it was found that 46% of the respondents are opined that locate old friends, 28% of the respondents are opined that meet new people, 11% of the respondents are opined that make photo albums and share pictures, 7% of the respondents are opined that talk the day away, 6% of the respondents are opined that seek advice and 3% of the respondents are opined that assist others.

Summary Of Findings

- Facebook is the most popular social media platform in India, followed by Whatsapp, Twitter, Youtube, Linkendin, and Friendster.
- India's population uses social media for a variety of purposes, such as meeting new people, reconnecting with old acquaintances, chatting endlessly, joining interest groups, making photo albums and sharing them, and feeling like they belong.
- Youth have had a 50% unfavourable influence from social networks.
- Social media harms education, business, and the workplace due to the high number of crimes committed there and the amount of time spent on social networking

activities. However, social media also has positive effects, which include facilitating open communication, expanding business contact opportunities, and making it simpler to stay in touch with friends and family.

Recommendations

- The government ought to incentivize individuals of all ages by lowering the cost of internet connection. This would enable folks to take advantage of social media platforms, which foster love and harmony among people, particularly those who reside in the nation.
- The primary harm that social media causes to our environment is fraud, so the government needs to figure out how to secure social networking sites to prevent hackers from committing these crimes.
- Social networking is a source of information, thus parents should expose their children to it to help them become more adept at understanding global events.
- To avoid having an adverse influence on their academic performance, young people should aim to avoid wasting time on social networking sites and instead wisely utilise the benefits of social networks.
- There have to be more education and awareness-raising programmes that emphasise using SNS safely. People must acquire data management skills for the Internet. Parents ought to participate in these educational activities as well.

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